

FABRICATION AND PERFORMANCE OF HYPERBRANCHED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES RESPONSIVE TO DIFFERENT STIMULI

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1 Introduction

Polyurethanes (PUs) have been used in a variety of applications such as thermoplastic elastomers, foams, fibers, adhesives, coating materials, and etc. Recently more interesting application has been focused on their shape memory properties because of their easy fabrication, low cost, good processing ability, high shape recoverability, and wide range of shape recovery temperature, compared to shape memory alloys [1,2]. Moreover different stimulus-responsive shape memory effects due to electric field and water stimuli as well as temperature are possible. Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are not electrically conductive materials, where external heat is required for the recovery, so their applications may be limited. A water-triggered SMP can be obtained by employing the hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups in the soft and hard segment of PU block copolymers, respectively. Block copolymers containing poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) as the hydrophilic groups have higher solubility in water due to their excellent hydrophilicity. For example, water-responsive SMP can be prepared by introducing polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (POSS) and PEO as hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups in the hard and soft segments, respectively.

A common technique to improve the recovery stress, mechanical properties, and to add multiple functionalities to SMPs is to mix various solid fillers with high mechanical properties. However, there is an inverse relationship between mechanical properties enhancement and shape recovery. The recovery ratio may decrease with an addition of fillers. Many of these issues can be alleviated by reducing filler loading, for example, by incorporation of small fraction of nanoscopic fillers or by designing the fillers in appropriate manner for

the polymer system. In case of micro-sized fillers, such as chopped carbon, glass or Kevlar fibers, the addition of 40-50 wt% of filler was necessary to achieve an improvement in polymer stiffness. The addition of 30 wt% carbon black to SMP also leads to a reduction in the shape recovery rate.

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are utilized as an ideal reinforcing agent for polymer composites due to their excellent thermal, mechanical, and electrical properties [3-5]. Particularly use of hyperbranched polymer for enhancing CNT dispersion suggests a scalable fabrication of high performance CNT composites. It is due to many advantages of the highly branched polymers such as good solubility, lower viscosity, presence of empty internal cavities, and extremely high density of functional groups.

This presentation discusses different stimulus-responsive shape memory performance of CNT composites with the hyperbranched polymers.

2 Experimental Sections

2.1 Materials

4,4'-Methylene bis(phenylisocyanate) (MDI) was purchased from Aldrich. Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)diol (PCL) and poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) were used for soft segments of polyurethanes. 1,4-Butanediol (BD) was obtained from Junsei Chemical, Japan. Multi-walled (MWNTs) and single-walled (SWNTs) carbon nanotubes were purchased from Iljin Nanotech, Korea.

2.2 Fabrication of Polymer-CNT Composites

For the fabrication of shape memory CNT-polymer composites, the hyperbranched polyurethanes (HBPU) based on PCL and PEG as a soft segment

were synthesized with MD, BD, and different branching compounds as shown in Fig.1. Vegetable oil based HBPU containing different hard segments were synthesized by two steps procedure. The prepolymer was prepared from the reaction of MDI and PCL. The required amount of PCL solution in dimethylformamide (DMF) was added dropwise through the dropping funnel into MDI solution in the vessel. After completion the addition of PCL, temperature was raised and maintained at 70 °C.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of synthesized HBPU, where D, L, and T refer to dendritic, linear, and terminal units, respectively [6].

CNTs were mixed with PUs after sonication using DMF as a solvent. In preparation of CNT composites, different methods may be available as shown in Fig. 2. In this study, conventional composites, functionalized-CNT composites, and in-situ polymerized composites were prepared and compared each other by using the linear and hyperbranched polyurethane polymers.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of different preparation methods of CNT composites with the polymers [5].

The shape fixity and shape recovery of the samples were measured using a tensile tester (UTM, Lloyd LR 50K) with a temperature controlled chamber. The samples were stretched to 100 %

elongation ratio at 60 °C, above the transition temperature with a constant drawing speed of 10 mm/min and kept for 5 min at same condition. The sample was then cooled at -25 °C and the temperature was kept for 15 minutes to fix the temporary elongation. After removal of applied stress, measurement of the deformed length was followed. The upper clamp was returned to original position and the specimen shrank from ϵ_m to ϵ_u due to instant elastic recovery. Finally, the sample was heated to 60 °C to allow shape recovery with the resulting specimen elongation returned to ϵ_p . The shape retention and shape recovery were calculated using the following equations:

$$\text{Shape retention (\%)} = \epsilon_u / \epsilon_m \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Shape recovery (\%)} = (\epsilon_m - \epsilon_p) / \epsilon_m \times 100 \quad (2)$$

3 Results and Discussion

Different characterization techniques were utilized to investigate the morphology and properties of shape memory polymer composites fabricated in different methods of conventional, in-situ polymerized, and functionalized CNTs composites. Choice of soft segment in PU resulted in obtaining the different stimulus-responsive shape memory effect. Fig. 3 shows typical stimulus-responsive shape memory behavior of the CNT-polymer composites, which is responsive to different stimulus such as temperature, electric field, and water. It was found that the shape recovery and shape retention values of CNT-polymer composites increased as the MWNT content increased. Performance of CNT composites at same CNT loading was also affected by fabrication methods, and presence of hyperbranched polymer was very effective in enhancing CNT dispersion and resultant shape memory effect.

Compared to the linear polymer composites with MWNTs, the hyperbranched polymer composites showed higher performance shape memory. Particularly, superior water-triggered shape memory effect could be demonstrated when PEG was used as a soft segment.

Thermo-mechanical cyclic tensile test was carried out by stress-strain measurements when the maximum strain was set at 100 %. All samples showed more than 80 % shape retention and shape recovery. We could observe that shape recovery and shape retention increased with an increase of hard

segment in HBPU due to higher inter and intra molecular interactions (Table 1).

Fig. 3. Typical shape recovery behavior of polymer-CNT composites responsive to different stimulus of temperature, electric field, and water.

Table 1. Cyclic shape recovery for pure HBPU and MWNT-PU composites

Sample	1st cycle (%)	2nd cycle (%)	3rd cycle (%)
Pure HBPU	82	79	77
MWNT-linear PU	85	80	76
MWNT-HBPU	89	86	83

For the CNT-HBPU composites, their stress-strain curves showed different shape memory behavior from that of the pure hyperbranched polymer, which is due to incorporation of CNTs into HBPU molecules. Particularly incorporation of CNT resulted in increasing modulus and showing the yielding behavior, compared with the pure hyperbranched polymer. It is associated with the enhanced CNT dispersion in HBPU matrix due to highly branched structure of HBPU [7, 8].

Relation between surface temperature and applied voltage of the samples was investigated. The temperature of the samples was measured using digital multi-meter with a non-contact temperature measuring system. The HBPU composites with low CNT content showed very low temperature after applying the voltage. For the composites at 5 wt%

MWNTs with hyperbranched and linear polyurethanes, the surface temperature increased sharply with time. However, the CNT-HBPU composites reached above the transition temperature very quickly in application of voltage compared to CNT-linear polymer composites, which is due to the better dispersion of CNTs in the HBPU matrix. It indicates that CNT-HBPU composites are more effective as the electroactive shape memory property.

4 Conclusions

The hyperbranched shape memory polymer-CNT composites responsive to different stimulus were prepared successfully. The composites demonstrated good electric- and water-responsive shape memory properties as well as thermo-responsive shape memory effect by choosing different soft segment and adding CNTs. Owing to enhanced CNT dispersion and fabrication, the CNT composites with hyperbranched polyurethane showed a steep increase in the mechanical properties as well as the shape memory properties with increasing the CNT content.

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